

Floor plan extraction from digital building models

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Abstract: Interior building data is gaining popularity, but while there is an abundance of exterior data for navigation and other purposes, the availability of indoor data is meagre. In this paper, we present an approach to extract simplified indoor data from digital building models, which are rich in interior information, and convert it to formats such as CityGML, IndoorGML, and OpenstreetMap to increase the availability of indoor data.

Keywords: IFC, CityGML, IndoorGML, OpenStreetMap

1. Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Accessibility, barriers, and the locations of facilities inside buildings are gaining greater public interest. There is a demand for seamless outdoor and indoor navigation and positioning as well as use of indoor data in commercial business applications and analyses. Accordingly, there is a popular trend to extend geospatial databases, map and routing services with indoor information, such that data and services can cater to broader applications.

Over the past decade, many researchers have addressed the topic by either extending geospatial data formats or by improving the quality and efficiency of indoor data acquisition. These works resort to existing 2D plans such as owner's as-built plans or publicly displayed escape plans such as the one used in the method developed by Tschorn et al. [1] for extracting building information from escape plans using computer vision methods, or they create 3D models from laser scans or photographic material, advancing developments in the fields of computer vision and photogrammetry. However, some of these methods require substantial manual effort, are labour-intensive, and at most semi-automatic. Given that the indoor layout is vulnerable to changes more frequently than the outdoor layout, it is challenging to keep it updated manually. This study will present a practical framework and pave the way for improvements in the production of indoor spatial data.

1.2 Objective and methodology

In this paper, we outline an approach for obtaining indoor data fully automatically by leveraging existing data from construction planning, where building information is produced in good quantity and quality. We develop conversion procedures that ingest building data as a source, extract 2.5D floor plans, map them to an intermediate model and finally derive data in three pertinent target formats: CityGML, IndoorGML, and OSM (OpenStreetMap). These procedures are ultimately to be integrated in a platform that allows owners of buildings and

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information about their publicly accessible interior spaces to contribute selected parts of their data to the common good as open data. The platform with its input and output is depicted schematically in Figure 1.

Figure 1: LevelOut Platform with input and output.

We work systematically from the source and target models towards the intermediate model and take a bottom-up, inductive approach: On the source side, we analyse the IFC (Industry Foundation Classes) schema and sample data from real-world projects for relevant patterns, implement checking routines and extract the input for conversion to the intermediate model. On the target side, we produce CityGML, IndoorGML and OSM sample data for a tailored sample project, identify commonalities of the schemas and design an intermediate model to generalize the output methods.

In this paper, we focus on the latter portion of the work – the production of data in three target formats as well as the derivation of the intermediate model. This paper is an extended version of the lightning talk presented at SOTM 2022 [2].

1.3 Related work

The integration of the geospatial and construction data has been extensively studied. Many researchers have investigated the integration of BIM (Building Information Modeling) and GIS (Geographic Information System) data in recent years. Due to the disparate ways that geometry and semantics are represented in each of the two areas, integrating the domains has proven to be challenging. In this section, we highlight a few papers about techniques for converting building data from IFC datasets to data models and formats from the geospatial domain.

For the automatic translation of IFC datasets to 3D building models in CityGML 2.0 LOD3 (Level of Detail 3), Donkers et al. proposed a three-step process [3]: IFC data is subjected to semantic filtering and extraction of pertinent IFC entity types, in particular *IfcSpace* and *IfcBuildingElement*. From their Constructive Solid Geometry and Boundary Representation geometries, the exterior and interior surface representation required for CityGML is deduced

and imperfections are corrected by morphological operations. Finally, geometrical, topological, and semantic adjustments lead to valid CityGML LOD3 output.

Different approaches to modelling 2D floor plans in CityGML 3.0 are suggested by Konde et al. [4]. The authors present two different methods to retrieve geometry information from IFC: The first method makes use of original IFC geometry types, whereas the second uses pre-processed triangulated geometry. Building elements such as openings, walls and doors are included.

The open-source tool `ifc2indoorgml` by Diakite et al. [5] generates IndoorGML data from IFC in three steps. First, significant information is gathered from the IFC data. Second, it is effectively structured as Linear Cell Complex (LCC). After that, the LCC data is processed to create IndoorGML data, including cell boundaries, nodes, edges, and topological relationships.

There is not a lot of published research on the conversion of BIM data to OSM. A converter from IFC to OSM data is developed as an open-source project called BIMtoOSM [6], currently included as a built-in component of the JOSM IndoorHelper plugin.

Despite the fact that numerous studies have been carried out, there is no concrete tool that exists to extract these data and increase the availability of indoor data. In our research, we focus on developing a method for automating the extraction of building floorplans and populating them into various destination formats.

2. Models

2.1 Target models

With the conversion, we target OpenStreetMap's Simple Indoor Tagging schema as well as two OGC (Open Geospatial Consortium) GML (Geography Markup Language) application schemas - CityGML 3.0 and IndoorGML 1.0. CityGML is dedicated to represent 3D city models, including building interiors, while IndoorGML targets indoor models for navigational purposes.

The CityGML conceptual model consists of a core and various domain-specific modules. Version 3.0 contains a new module called construction as the base for common elements across the building, tunnel, and bridge modules. We employ the core, building, and construction modules. IndoorGML has core and thematic modules as well. The fundamental semantics are contained in the core module, and additional modules provide application-specific additions, for example for navigation purposes. We employ the core and navigation modules in our work.

The most basic form of indoor mapping with the OpenStreetMap SIT (Simple Indoor Tagging) schema is simple point-of-interest mapping with an added level tag. The tags `min_level` and `max_level` are introduced at the building level to indicate indoor coverage. More detail building interior can be modelled by using tags for common indoor components like room, area, wall, and corridor. The level tag is shared by every component of a certain floor.

2. Models

2.2 Intermediate model

Figure : UML diagram of the intermediate model

Based on the commonalities determined from the three target formats, we derive an intermediate model. This model will serve as the mapping target for pertinent entities extracted from IFC and provides the input for the final creation of the conversion results. The UML (Unified Modeling Language) class diagram in Figure 2 shows the classes, attributes, and associations of the preliminary intermediate model.

We identified the classes Corner, Room, Storey, and Building as being most important for the intermediate model, followed by Wall, Slab and Opening. The classes are named after the semantics of the objects, but comprise both semantic and geometric attributes together. The merge of semantics and geometry proved to appropriately reflect the antithetical modelling paradigms in OGC GML application schemas and OSM tagging schemas and allows us to address both “philosophies” from within the intermediate model.

2.3 Model Mapping

We took a bottom-up approach and started with programmatic production of CityGML, IndoorGML and OSM data for a tailored sample project. During this process, the selection of elements from the target formats listed in Table 1, columns 2-4, evolved naturally. From there, we identified common input needed for the instantiation and wiring of target objects. In a systematic refactoring process, the parameters of the generating functions were moved to attributes of dedicated classes which subsequently constitute the intermediate model.

Intermediate model	CityGML	IndoorGML	OSM (S3DB, SIT)
Building	core:Building	IndoorFeatures	way (building=yes) S3DB
Storey	core:Storey	not reflected	way (indoor=level) SIT level= <storey> shared
Room	core:BuildingRoom, gml:Polygon	CellSpace/State, gml:Polygon, gml:Point	way (indoor=room) SIT
Wall	bldg:BuildingConstructive Element	CellSpaceBoundary/ Transition	way (indoor=wall) SIT
Corner	gml:Point/PointList	gml:Point/PointList	node (no tags)

Table 1: Mapping of model elements from the intermediate model to the three target models

It must be noted that representation of mappings between information models in a tabulated form does only serve an illustrative purpose. It cannot capture the full details of the pre and post conditions of a specific transformation piece.

3. Implementation

The target environment, where the conversion will ultimately be executed, is the Opensource BIMserver [7]. It provides effective means of accessing IFC data selectively and in a streaming fashion in a client-server application. Thus, we use Java to implement the population of the intermediate model and the further conversion. We selected respective Java libraries to lean on for the three target formats.

For working with OSM data, we employ *osm4j*, which aids with reading and writing OSM data in different formats, for example XML (Extensible Markup Language), JSON (Javascript Object Notation) and binary formats. . The core package offers classes such as *OsmNode*, *OsmWay* and *OsmRelation* for OSM data representation. Besides *osm4j-core*, we use the *osm4j-xml* package to write OSM XML.

To write 3D city models encoded in CityGML, we use *citygml4j*. The library can write CityGML and CityJSON based on the conceptual model. We employ the *citygml4j-core* and *citygml4j-xml* packages. *citygml4j* is based on JAXB (Jakarta XML Binding, a technology to bind Java classes to XML elements) and provides a higher-level API for instantiating a JAXB object graph. For IndoorGML, we use JAXB-generated classes on a lower level and resort to Alexey Valikov's JAXB bindings for OGC schemas [8].

4. Validation

We use test data from a basic two-storey residential building to verify our intermediate model. There are three rooms on each level of the building, accounting to a total of six rooms. Later, the intermediate model will be put to the test using data from two sets of university buildings as well as data from a municipal administration centre under construction in Dresden.

4.1 Plausibility tests

As a first simple form of validation, we use various tools, to examine the output produced by the conversion procedures visually. For the CityGML data, we mostly rely on the FZK viewer [9], a viewer for semantic models in the fields of BIM and GIS. IndoorGML is examined using the desktop version of STEMLab's InViewer [10], a viewer built on Unity3D to display IndoorGML data. To assess and explore the OSM data, we use JOSM [11], an extensible editor for OSM data.

Apart from inspection and plausibility checking via a GUI (Graphical User Interface), opening and parsing files in those applications also serves as a form of implicit validation for syntactic and semantic correctness. Sometimes, these applications also log validation errors upon import. Other non-GUI applications can be used to achieve this as well: The 3D City Database Importer/Exporter [12], for example, is an open-source software suite that includes a database schema and tools for working with 3D city models based on the CityGML standard. During import into the 3D City Database Importer/Exporter, the XML is validated against the schema.

4. Validation

City Doctor [13] is another application to examine, check, and correct the syntax, semantics, and geometry of digital 3D city models. It is, however, not open source but only free to use in its most basic form.

While the CityGML 3.0 conceptual model has been officially endorsed by the OGC, work on the CityGML 3.0 GML Encoding specification is still ongoing. That is why many tools, such as 3D City Database Importer/Exporter and City Doctor mentioned do not yet implement CityGML 3.0. As soon as the encoding is released, more tools can be expected to upgrade to support version 3.0.

4.2 Syntactic and semantic validation

To make sure that the requirements of the OGC standards are met, CityGML and IndoorGML files are validated more formally. Since both standards are based on GML with its predominant encoding in XML, they can be validated against the respective XSD (XML Schema Definition) schemas. The validation makes sure that the fundamental syntactic rules are fulfilled and that the document is thus well-formed and complies with the guidelines established by the schema.

The OGC provides a compliance program with test suites for endorsed standards. Concrete files are checked for compliance with the standard specifications as defined by the XSDs, but also semantic constraints beyond that. These tests can be executed in various ways, for example from an Integrated development environment (IDE), from the command line, via Docker, through the OGC Test harness, and a Rest API (Application Programming Interface). We utilize the OGC test harness (Team Engine). For IndoorGML 1.0, there is a beta version of the test suite. For CityGML 3.0 there is no test suite yet.

For OSM, there are no XSD schemas available. The schema is very simple though and accordingly little error-prone. Complexity and risk of deficiencies arise from the flexible tagging scheme. That is why tools for validating the higher-level semantics and tagging completeness are necessary. One such tool for validating indoor data in OSM has been created in the Accessible Maps project at TU Dresden: SIT MapChecker [14] is built on top of OsmlnEdit and examines the indoor element's adherence to the SIT schema. Additionally, it detects violations of the geometric and topological integrity, such as building overlaps, objects crossing building bounds or inaccessible spaces. Finally, it also checks for additional tags relevant to accessibility of buildings in order to foster mapping with achievements as incentives.

4.4 Geometric and topological integrity

CityGML and IndoorGML features are represented using geometry classes defined in ISO 19107. The international standard defines geometric primitives such as GM_Point (0D), GM_Curve (1D), GM_Surface (2D), and GM_Solid (3D). Due to the nature of floor plans, we make use of primitives and aggregates up to 2D only. Tools such as Val3dity [15] allow for the validation of the geometric and topological integrity of the geometry. Currently Val3dity offers support for only IndoorGML files and CityJSON files rather than CityGML files, but this is sufficient for our purpose, since IndoorGML is based on the same GML geometries.

5. Conclusion

5.1 Summary

In summary, our research strives to enhance and enrich the available indoor data and combine it with the available outdoor geospatial datasets. We exclusively target open data formats, aim to publish generated resulting data sets as open data and release the conversion methods as open source code to the general audience. Building owners have the choice to make their information accessible to the public, aiding in the process of volunteer mapping. Apart from the declared project goals, this paper contributes an overview of the suitable tools for working with indoor data in the targeted formats.

5.2 Limitations and future work

There are certain restrictions in the current work, some of which will be resolved as the work advances. We will utilize additional, more realistic sample data to evaluate the conversion. Currently, the IFC data from the municipal administration centre is being processed to extract the pertinent entities. For now, we are employing the so-called thin wall model for the floorplans. The thick wall model is an alternate option that will be studied later to create variation of the floor plans. For the model to be complete, doors, walls, connections between the various building levels, and accessibility details must all be included. Last but not least, when tools for validating CityGML version 3.0 files become available in the future, we intend to validate them. As mentioned in the validation section, OSM data will also be verified using the SIT-MapChecker tool.

5.3 Outlook and impact

The output of this endeavour will offer a practical tool for extracting and enhancing the indoor data of publicly accessible buildings. In combination with indoor positioning systems, indoor navigation will serve one of the primary applications. It also provides the foundation for broader applications such as AI-based navigation. It can also cater to commercial applications such as expanding business by locating hotspots of sale. It helps in improved public transportation and accessibility of public areas.

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References

[1] Tschorn, Georg; Kray, Christian; Broelemann, Klaus (2013): Extracting indoor map data from public escape plans on mobile devices (Master's thesis). Westfälische Wilhelms-Universität Münster, Münster, Germany.

References

- [2] Tauscher, Helga; Krishnakumar, Subhashini; Heigener, Dominik, (2022): Floor plan extraction from digital building models. In Proceedings of the Academic Track at State of the Map 2022, Florence, Italy, 19-21.08.2022, pp. 58-61. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7004633.
- [3] Donkers, Sjors; Ledoux, Hugo; Zhao, Junqiao; Stoter, Jantien (2015): Automatic conversion of IFC datasets to geometrically and semantically correct CityGML LOD3 buildings. In Transactions in GIS 20 (4), pp. 547–569. DOI: 10.1111/tgis.12162.
- [4] Konde, Amol; Tauscher, Helga; Biljecki, Filip; Crawford, James (2018): Floor plans in CityGML. In ISPRS Ann. Photogramm. Remote Sens. Spatial Inf. Sci. IV-4/W6, pp. 25–32. DOI: 10.5194/isprs-annals-IV-4-W6-25-2018.
- [5] Diakite, Abdoulaye A.; Díaz-Vilariño, Lucia; Biljecki, Filip; Isikdag, Ümit; Simmons, Scott; Li, Ki-Joune; Zlatanova, Sisi. (2022): ifc2indoorgml: An open-source tool for generating IndoorGML from IFC. In Int. Arch. Photogramm. Remote Sens. Spatial Inf. Sci. XLIII-B4-2022, pp. 295–301. DOI: 10.5194/isprs-archives-XLIII-B4-2022-295-2022.
- [6] Schmidt, Rebecca (2023): BIMtoOSM (JSOM IndoorHelper plugin), <https://github.com/rebeccasc/BIMtoOSM> [Accessed 29.01.2023].
- [7] The open source BIM collective (2023): BIMserver, v1.5.183, <https://github.com/opensourceBIM/BIMserver> [Accessed 29.01.2023].
- [8] Valikov, Alexey (2023): JAXB bindings for OGC schemas, snapshot version commit 18ce899 <https://github.com/highsource/ogc-schemas> [Accessed 29.01.2023].
- [9] KIT IAI (2022): FZK Viewer 6.5, <https://www.iai.kit.edu/1648.php> [Accessed 23.01.2023].
- [10] STEMLab (2023): Inviewer-Desktop (af9dea39), <https://github.com/STEMLab/InViewer-Desktop> [Accessed 23.01.2023].
- [11] OSM community (2023): JOSM, version r18622, <https://josm.openstreetmap.de/> [Accessed 23.01.2023].
- [12] 3D City Database Importer/Exporter v5.3.0 (2022), <https://github.com/3dcitydb/importer-exporter> [Accessed 23.01.2023].
- [13] Casper, Egbert (2016): City Doctor 2.2.1, <https://www.citydoctor.eu> [Accessed 23.01.2023].
- [14] Schmalfuß-Schwarz, Jan; Striegl, Julian (2021): Analyse Tool für Simple Indoor Tagging (Analysis tool for Simple Indoor Tagging). In: Proc. of FOSSGIS conference, June 2021, online.
- [15] Ledoux, Hugo. (2020): Are your IndoorGML files valid? In ISPRS Ann. Photogramm. Remote Sens. Spatial Inf. Sci. VI-4/W1-2020, pp. 109–118. DOI: 10.5194/isprs-annals-VI-4-W1-2020-109-2020.
- [16] Levelout project (2023): BIMserver plugins and web application for the Levelout project, <https://bauinformatik.github.io/levelout>.